

Educational resources for technical stakeholders in training

1. Introduction

The educational resources of the In Silico World project aim to train or retrain different key groups in the development and use of in silico models in the medical field. One of these key groups is the group of master and PhD students that are being trained in a technical discipline as mathematics or engineering. Concrete lecture material was developed in the format of a mini-course that contains three important topics in the field of in silico medicine. A shortened version of the lecture material was tested by a participant group. Its impact was then evaluated based on a pre- and post-questionnaire, on the one hand, and an in-depth analysis of the pre-defined learning goals, on the other hand. Based on the results, recommendations on the further use and optimization of the lecture material are formulated.

2. Methods

While many topics related to in silico medicine are of interest and an initial introduction can only contain a limited number of topics, a selection of topics was first of all made by determining intended learning outcomes for the considered participant group at the initial stage. In order to develop educational resources, a mini-course was composed. This mini-course contains three modules, each on a different topic, with some of them being subdivided into two parts. The mini-course aims to make the participants familiar with some basic concepts of in silico modeling in medicine and get a view on the state-of-the-art research. An overview of the considered topics in the mini-course, with the subdivision in parts, and the total duration of each module can be found in table 1. A description of the different modules of the mini-course can be found in appendix A.

Table 1: Overview of the topics and the duration for the modules of the developed mini-course.

Module	Topic	Duration full version (min.)	Duration short version (min.)
1	What is a model?	90	20
	Introduction to in silico medicine	90	25
2	Regulatory aspects	25	25
	VVUQ: hands-on (video + hands-on)	25 + 70	25 + 10
3	Agent-based models	60	25

In order to collect data and feedback on the composed lecture material, a test version of the mini-course was composed based on a selection of fragments from the video recordings. This selection allows the participants to grasp the main concepts of the lecture in a limited time frame. Next to the selection of fragments, the test version included a pre- and post-questionnaire, as well as an evaluation form after each topic of the mini-course. The total time of the test version was estimated at two hours and a half. This short version was tested by eleven participants, with a background in biomedical engineering with a focus on biomechanics.

The pre- and post-questionnaire assessed how aware the participants were on different concepts related to in silico medicine and to which extent they agreed to statements that expressed the potential added value of this domain before and after going through the lecture material, by selecting

one of five predefined categories. The categories were not aware, slightly aware, moderately aware, very aware and extremely aware for the questions and strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree for the statements. Those categories were translated into a numerical score, ranging from one to five. A histogram of the given scores was made for the answers of the pre- and post-questionnaire as well as the difference in pre- and post-score per participant.

Next to the data analysis based on the questionnaires, an in-depth analysis was performed as well. In the evaluation forms, the participants were asked to indicate the three key aspects they wanted to take home. By relating these aspects to the learning goals of each module, an indication was found of the extent to which the learning goals were effectively achieved. Moreover, the stakeholders had the possibility to include written feedback in the form as well.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analysis of questionnaires

The initial average scores given to the questions of the pre-questionnaires are for most modeling concepts in the upper range of the awareness categories. This is not surprising seen the technical background of the participants. When considering the histograms of the individual scores (see appendix B), this observation is less clear, due to the spread in prior perception of awareness of the considered concepts. While some variation in the scores given to the different statements was found as well, a clear tendency towards the highest scores was observed, in the histograms as well as in the average value. This indicates a strong initial believe in the potential added value of in silico medicine. The fact that the considered participants voluntarily decided to participate and are being trained in the field of in silico modeling in medicine might of course impose an intrinsic bias to the initial interest in the topic.

When comparing the average results of the pre- and post-questionnaire, an increase in the average score is seen for most of the questions (see figure 1). The extent to which there is an increase, strongly differs. The increase related to awareness in computational biomechanics, artificial intelligence and uncertainty quantification is limited, while a clear difference in the pre- and post-questionnaire scores is observed regarding the awareness of agent-based and molecular models. The prior awareness might explain a major part of the difference in increase. Indeed, as the initial awareness on computational, artificial intelligence and uncertainty quantification was already very high, no major increase can be expected. Moreover, this high awareness suggests that the participants are familiar to these concepts. A mini-course, where there is no time for an in depth study of the topics, is not expected to increase the knowledge the participants already possessed. The prior knowledge regarding agent-based and molecular models was, however, much lower, leaving much more room to increase the existing awareness.

The awareness of verification and validation slightly decreases, which is surprising, seen the explicit attention that was given to the topic in the second module. In this respect, it is interesting to point out that the complete version of this part contains a video lecture, some concept questions and a hands-on assignment. The latter was discarded in the test version, which might affect the understanding of the participants.

Figure 1: (a) Mean scores of the questions in the pre- and post-questionnaire regarding the perceived awareness of various *in silico* medicine concepts. (b) Mean scores of the extent of agreement to the statements in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

The participant-specific differences between the pre- and post-questionnaire indicates either a status quo or slight increase in the given score. Only in a few cases, the awareness was perceived to be lower after going through the lecture material. The participant-specific results illustrate that not only on average, but also on an individual level, a quite consistent increase was observed, in particular for those concepts where a large average effect was found as well (see appendix B). For the questions regarding verification and validation, where a slight overall decrease was found, it can be noticed that that the range of post-questionnaire scores is still narrow and situated in the upper half of the scores. Participants with a strong decrease in awareness, which could potentially relate to confusing lecture material, were not observed.

In the short version, the impact of the lecture material, strongly varied for the different modules of the mini-course. Considering the complete test version is expected to result in an increased awareness-score for verification and validation. For the other awareness concepts, considering the complete mini-course is expected to have a similar result. It seems that amount of prior knowledge is an important factor. Thus, longer and more specific courses will be needed to enhance the perceived awareness of already well-known concepts.

While the interest in following these courses was not directly assessed, the extent of agreement gives an indication of the participants' believe in the potential added value of integrating *in silico* modeling in medicine. Although the initial believe showed already a high score, the lecture material overall succeeded to further increase this believe. Despite a few participants indicating a slightly decreased score, the lowest scores disappeared in the post-questionnaire result, meaning that all participants are (strongly) convinced in the added value of *in silico* medicine. This group of participants is, therefore, expected to be motivated to further deepen their knowledge by follow more in depth courses and, thus, continue their education.

3.2. In-depth analysis of learning goals

The extent to which the learning goals could be identified in the key aspects provided by the participants, is illustrated in figure 2. The height of the bars indicate the fraction of participants that provided key aspects that could be related to a specific learning goal (see appendix A). The color of the bars shows an *a priori* identification of the extent to which the learning goals were covered in the test

version of the lecture material. Green, orange and red, respectively, refer to a learning goal that is well, moderately or not covered in the test version.

Figure 2: Frequency of indication of learning of (a) module 1 part 1, (b) module 1 part 2, (c) module 2 part 1, (d) module 2 part 2 and (e) module 3. The height of the colored bar indicates the fraction of participants that provided key aspects related to the considered learning goals. The color of the bar as well as the background indicates how well the learning goal was covered in the test version of the lecture material, with green, orange and red respectively referring to well, moderately and not covered.

While the relation between the provided key aspects and the learning goals is subject to interpretation and the frequency of indication depends on the number of learning goals for each modules, the analysis gives an estimation of the combined effect of the aspects that are of interest to the participants and the information that the participant retains from the lecture material.

Overall, most of the learning goals were indicated in the key aspects of, at least, part of the participants. The frequency of indication and its relation to the amount of attention that was spent on the goal in the test version of the mini-course was, however, variable. Some of the learning goals that were expected to be well covered in the short version of the lecture material, were indeed frequently indicated in the key aspects of the participants. This confirms that, at least, part of the content of the lecture material was effectively grasped by the participants. Surprisingly, some of the learning goals that were only moderately or not covered in the test version were still (frequently) identified, while some of the well covered learning goals were not often indicated. On the one hand, this might indicate that a learning goal should be addressed more explicitly in order to ensure that the participants grasp the envisioned content, in particular for those goals that have a lower frequency of indication than expected. On the other hand, this effect could also be related to the interest of the participants and, therefore, provide information on the topics the participants are interested in, which can contribute to the further optimization of the lecture material.

First of all, learning goals that were considered to be well covered in the test version and that were often indicated as key aspects should retain their importance in an optimized version of the mini-course. Learning goals that were frequently indicated, while the goal was only moderately covered, do not imply an immediate change of the lecture material. In the complete mini-course, more attention is already provided to the considered goal, which is expected to be sufficient. Nevertheless, these topics are expected to be of interest to the participants. In more specialized or elaborate courses, it could, therefore, be relevant to provide more in-depth information on the topic.

Learning goals that were only indicated to a limited extent, compared to the *a priori* expectations, deserve additional attention in the optimization of the lecture material. Indeed, the first stage is to reconsider the importance of the learning goal. If the learning goal is still considered to be important, then the way the content is provided should be reconsidered. Making the mini-course more interactive or adding more motivating examples could contribute to help the participant in grasping the content.

Moreover, it should be noted that the current evaluation format, i.e. asking for three key aspects, is prone to interpretation. Therefore, an assessment with multiple choice questions could provide valuable objective information on the grasped knowledge of the participants.

4. Outlook

Based on a quantitative analysis, the effect of the lecture material on the awareness of in silico medicine and belief in its potential added value is promising. While the size of the test group was limited, these results indicate that a small amount of lecture material already has an impact, in particular for topics whereof the participants had a minor prior awareness. To further enhance the awareness and knowledge of concepts they already know quite well, more in depth lecture material is required. A combination of introductions to new or recent findings and technologies and in depth courses is, consequently, recommended to continue the training of stakeholders with a technical background.

The in-depth analysis indicates to which extent the learning goals were considered to be key aspects by the participants. This gives combined information of the interest of the participants and how well they grasped the learning goals. It is strongly recommended to include this information in further optimization of the lecture material, in particular for those learning goals that resulted in a lower frequency of identification compared to the initial expectations.

The written feedback identified mainly that the lecture on VVUQ was sometimes confusing in the current implementation. Adding more specific feedback to the provided concept questions and including the hands-on part of the module, as in the complete version of the mini-course, might already provide a strong improvement.

Moreover a short self-assessment after following the mini-course could help the stakeholder to assess their knowledge on the discussed topics in a more objective way, compared to the questionnaire where only their perception of awareness was queried. As a proof of concept, some assessment-questions were already implemented to showcase the suggested improvement of the lecture material.

Appendix A – Modules of mini-course with learning goals

Module 1

Part A. What is a model?

A model is a commonly used term, but a description of what a model is, is much harder to find. This module tries to answer the general question “What is a model?”, which is relevant for many disciplines, including in silico medicine. The search for an answer leads to a convoluted journey along different perspectives, descriptions and types of models.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Outline different definitions of “what is a model” related to different ways to address the topic;
2. Mention the relationship between scientific method, purpose of science and models (e.g., falsification strategies, theories testing);
3. Categorize and use scientific models;
4. Understand differences between experiments and numerical models;
5. Define the assessment plan of a model’s credibility;
6. Execute the VV&UQ (Verification, Validation & Uncertainty Quantification);
7. Summarize how VV&UQ (Verification, Validation & Uncertainty Quantification) and ASME VV-40 (Model risk, Credibility factors, Applicability) work.

Part B. Introduction to in silico medicine

This course module introduces the participants to some of the general concepts of in silico medicine technologies and discusses the related opportunities and limitations.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Understand the complexity of dealing with predictions about human health;
2. Identify the origins of barriers against adoption of in silico technologies (complexity, redundancy, stochasticity, culture);
3. Summarize first examples of Digital Twins and In Silico Trials developed;
4. Assess the value of the In Silico Trials in the development of new medical products;
5. Outline the 3R concept that led In Silico Trials;
6. Illustrate how In silico technologies might be of help to ensure and extend the healthcare given how the world population is growing;
7. Explain what the Virtual Human Twin will be.

Module 2

Part A: Regulatory aspects

With the perspective to integrate in silico medicine in the process of diagnosis, treatment development and treatment selection, a regulatory framework is unavoidable. This course module provides an

overview of the state-of-the-art regarding the regulatory framework and the aspects that are still lacking.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Illustrate the importance of regulatory pathways;
2. Identify the main regulatory authorities in the United States and the EU in the framework of biomedical in silico models;
3. Classify a computational model as digital twin or as in silico trial methodology and formulate the implications on the required regulatory pathways;
4. Formulate which standard is currently used to assess the credibility of a computational model;
5. Identify relevant regulatory guides for a given application including a biomedical in silico model.

Part B: VVUQ hands-on

In the framework of in silico modelling is not only the technical development of the models essential, but also its evaluation. This evaluation comprises a combination of verification, validation and uncertainty quantification of the model. In this course module, these concepts are introduced and the participants will practice them based on concept questions and apply them in an example model of an aortic aneurysm.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Distinguish between Clinical Trials and In Silico Clinical Trials and comprehend their respective advantages and disadvantages;
2. Summarize the different steps listed in the ASME V&V40 document;
3. Identify the question of interest, the context of use and the model risk for a specific example of a computational model within the framework of in silico medicine;
4. Classify credibility activities of a computational model into verification or validation;
5. Execute code and calculation verification;
6. Analyze and interpret the results of an uncertainty and sensitivity analysis;
7. Illustrate model form selection of a computational model;
8. Understand the concept of comparators in the context of model validation.

Module 3: Agent-based models

While many in silico medicine models represent the aggregated behaviour of a tissue or body part, an agent-based models utilizes an alternative approach, where individual agents and their mutual interaction play a central role. The course module explains the general model principles, their benefits, and illustrates the modelling technique with potential applications.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Formulate the general working principle of an agent-based model;
2. Clarify the role and the main features of an agent in agent-based models;
3. Formulate advantages and disadvantages of a bottom-up and top-down modeling approach;

4. Relate the use of agent-based modeling to a bottom-up approach in in silico modeling;
5. Illustrate the use of agent-based models with a state-of-the-art research example.

Appendix B – Participant-specific results

Question 1: Computational mechanics

Figure B1: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 1 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 1 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 2: Multiscale modeling

Figure B2: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 2 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 2 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 3: Artificial intelligence

Figure B3: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 3 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 3 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 4: Pharmacokinetic models

Figure B4: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 4 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 4 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 5: (Bayesian) network models

Figure B5: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 5 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 5 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 6: Agent based models

Figure B6: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 6 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 6 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 7: Molecular modeling

Figure B7: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 7 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 7 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 8: Uncertainty quantification

Figure B8: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 8 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 8 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 9: Verification

Figure B9: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 9 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 9 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 10: Validation

Figure B10: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 10 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 10 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 1: Accelerate adoption of new medical device or treatment

Figure B11: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 1 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 1 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 2: Decrease number of clinical trials conducted on humans or animals

Figure B12: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 2 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 2 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 3: Decrease cost to develop medical device or treatment

Figure B13: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 3 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 3 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.